

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Report on enabling technology for ultra low emittance ring

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ABSTRACT

I.FAST Task 7.2, Enabling technologies for ultra-low emittance rings, focuses on networking in the field of low emittance rings, which is dominated by the recent upgrades of the X-ray storage rings and the exploitation of synergies with existing and future e^+/e^- colliders. To achieve the goals of the task, Task 7.2 organized five international workshops and one joint experimental campaign, while the task partners also strengthened networking among themselves through regular task meetings where workshop plans and scientific topics were discussed. Networking activities such as workshop organization were followed by networking activities among the Task partners, resulting in successful workshops and strengthened networking among the Task partners and the research fields of ultra-low emittance rings. Through all these activities and efforts, Task 7.2 has realized the strengthening of networking between accelerator-related institutions in research and industry with diversity and inclusion.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

Many key technologies and in-depth knowledge are required to realize ultra-low emittance rings, which provide high quality beams for synchrotron light sources, damping rings and e^+/e^- circular colliders. Networking activities to share knowledge and experience on the key technologies strongly promote new projects for ultra-low emittance rings, and also stimulate innovation and synergies arising from networking with other scientific research and industrial areas. I.FAST Task 7.2 aims at networking in the area of ultra-low emittance rings by organizing workshops where participants can share the information and knowledge to strongly promote new projects on ultra-low emittance rings.

The partners of I.FAST Task 7.2 are fully motivated to organize the workshops and other scientific events such as joint experiments, and have successfully organized five international workshops and one joint experiment so far, through regular monthly meetings since May 2021 to cultivate each other and discuss the latest scientific topics and workshop organization.

Through the networking activities carried out so far, the objectives of I.FAST Task 7.2, namely networking, have been achieved to the extent that new networking has taken place in the field of ultra-low emittance rings.

1 Introduction

In the scientific fields based on synchrotron radiation and e^+/e^- colliders, the demand for high quality ultra-low emittance electron/positron beams is now becoming much higher. In ultra-low emittance rings, transverse beam sizes typically reach the spatial diffraction limit in the keV range of synchrotron radiation photons. Such high-quality beams enable high brightness synchrotron radiation sources and high luminosity e^+/e^- colliders to contribute to a wide range of scientific, engineering and technological fields. However, the realization of such high-quality beams requires scientific and technological breakthroughs in several areas of accelerator physics and technology. Given the complexity of an accelerator system, which consists of many hardware devices, and networking activities that enable the exchange and sharing of information, knowledge, and experience accompanied by technology transfer, are in a high demand for ultra-low emittance ring projects.

In response to these requirements, the partners in I.FAST Task 7.2 are engaged in enabling technologies up to innovations for ultra-low emitting rings and in strengthening networking activities in these areas. This is achieved by organizing scientific events such as international workshops that provide opportunities for information and knowledge exchange and publishing a summary of the workshops as I.FAST publication. In addition, members of Task 7.2 organized and will continue to organize joint experiments on accelerator physics and technology, allowing participants to work together on the same experimental topics. This is based on the monthly meetings where the Task 7.2 partners prepare the workshops, the experiments and exchange information on the latest topics, research results and innovations related to ultra-low emittance rings.

In this deliverable, we summarize our networking activities such as workshops and joint experiments that have been done so far. We also present a plan for the next workshop, which will be organized in March 2025 after the submission of this deliverable report.

2 Workshop Organization

2.1 WORKSHOP ON BEAM DIAGNOSTICS AND DYNAMICS IN ULTRA-LOW EMITTANCE RINGS (ONLINE)

Synchrotron radiation sources and e^+/e^- colliders require high quality beams with ultra-low emittance and high beam stability. In order to assess beam quality and stability, technological breakthroughs in beam diagnostics are needed to evaluate the beam quality and stability achieved at levels never reached by previous accelerators. To guide the development of the beam diagnostics system in the optimal direction for ultra-low-emittance beams, it is essential to improve the understanding of beam dynamics and to facilitate the exchange of information and knowledge between the diagnostics side and the beam dynamics side. Based on these ideas, the workshop on beam diagnostics and dynamics in ultra-low emittance rings was organized [1]. The workshop period was from April 25 to 29, 2022, during the international pandemic, and it was challenging to proceed with the workshop activities. However, the workshop was conducted online by the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) with participants from around the world. The workshop included sessions on beam diagnostics and beam dynamics with the aim of exchanging information and knowledge between the two sides of beam diagnostics and beam dynamics. The contents of the workshop were briefly summarized and published as the I.FAST project report [2].

Workshop statistics:

20 presentations in 2.5 days, 81 participants from several accelerator research fields

2.2 LOW EMITTANCE RINGS – PERMANENT MAGNET WORKSHOP

Nowadays, permanent magnet technology is strongly focused, accompanied by technological progress and the demand to reduce the energy consumption for accelerator operation. Motivated by these backgrounds, the Workshop on Permanent Magnets was jointly organized by LEAPS-PerMaLIC [3] and I.FAST in Trieste from November 14th to 15th with the local support of Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste. In the workshop, the state-of-the-art topics related to permanent magnet systems were widely discussed with the participants from all over the world, not only from accelerator institutes but also from industry. The workshop comprehensively covered scientific and technological topics related to permanent magnets and focused on innovations with a wide range of discussions, including the production and industrialization of permanent magnets. The workshop was a great success and the contents of the workshop, including the presentation slides, were published on the Indico workshop website [4].

Workshop statistics:

19 presentations in 1.5 days, 42 participants from research and industry

2.3 LOW EMITTANCE RINGS WORKSHOP

The concept of ultra-low emittance rings is based on a variety of key technologies and beam dynamics knowledge relevant for achieving high beam quality. To share the latest information, experience, and knowledge covering a wide range of accelerator physics and technology, the partners of Task 7.2 organized an international workshop, the Low Emittance Rings Workshop 2024, at CERN from February 13th to 16th, 2024. The aim of the workshop was to share knowledge and information on ultra-low emittance rings across a wide range of design approaches and performance goals that drive key technologies, including lattice design, optics measurement and correction, nonlinear dynamics, magnet design, beam stability, feedback and diagnostics, ring design challenges, collective effects, harmonic cavity design and experiments, energy calibration, machine learning and artificial intelligence. In particular, a full session organized in collaboration with I.FAST WP 11 (Sustainable Concepts and Technologies) [5] was dedicated to power consumption, energy efficiency and sustainability. All the presentations discussed were state-of-the-art topics worldwide, and the participants were able to strengthen the network in the field of ultra-low emittance rings, including light source storage rings, damping rings, and e^+/e^- circular colliders, by sharing knowledge and the latest advances in the field. The total number of registered participants reached nearly one hundred, and the participants came from various fields of accelerator physics and technology, including institutes and industrial areas worldwide, with diversity. The workshop reached many relevant conclusions, and the contents of the workshop were summarized and published on the Indico workshop website [6].

Workshop statistics:

60 presentations in 4 days, 99 participants from research and industry

2.4 WORKSHOP ON BUNCH-BY-BUNCH FEEDBACK SYSTEMS AND RELATED BEAM DYNAMICS

In ultra-low emittance rings, due to the high quality of the beams, collective beam instabilities can be stimulated by interactions between the beams and the environment, such as RF cavities and vacuum chamber walls, leading to degradation of the beam quality. Especially for low emittance rings, the bore radius of the magnets (magnetic gap widths) becomes smaller, resulting in a small vacuum chamber size. Collective beam instabilities associated with the small vacuum chamber size and NEG coating technology, which is becoming a common method for low emittance rings, become relevant issues. Accordingly, bunch-by-bunch feedback systems are becoming one of the indispensable devices to ensure beam quality in ultra-low emittance rings. The bunch-by-bunch feedback systems have been installed in several ring-based synchrotron light sources, damping rings and e^+/e^- circular colliders. The aim of the workshop on bunch-by-bunch feedback systems was to strengthen the networking in the field of feedback systems to exchange the latest information and experiences that feedback system specialists have developed so far. It should be emphasized that people involved in the development of bunch-by-bunch feedback systems worldwide attended the workshop together

and shared their knowledge and experience, which was one of the results of networking activities. The workshop on the KIT campus from 3 to 6 March 2024 was jointly organised by SOLEIL and KIT, both two partners of I.FAST Task 7.2. It led to relevant and sufficient scientific and technological conclusions. The contents of the workshop were published on the Indico workshop website [7].

Workshop statistics:

18 presentations in 3 days, 43 participants from research and industrial areas

2.5 WORKSHOP ON INJECTORS FOR STORAGE RING BASED LIGHT SOURCES

Immediately after the workshop on bunch-by-bunch feedback systems and related beam dynamics, the workshop on injectors for storage ring based light sources was held at KIT from March 6 to 8. The organization of these two workshops aimed at synergies between two different scientific fields. In ultra-low emittance rings, injectors such as booster synchrotrons supply beams to the main storage rings, which serve as light sources. To ensure stable beam operation of the main storage rings, the injectors must be operated to deliver high quality beams to the main rings while maintaining high stability. The Injector Workshop also aimed to share the latest information and experience on the operation and upgrading of injectors in operation and under consideration, accompanied by new projects for the main storage ring light sources. Since the Injector Workshop was held immediately after the Bunch-by-Bunch Feedback Workshop, several participants from the Feedback Workshop also attended the Injector Workshop, and several discussions were held using technical terms from the Bunch-by-Bunch Feedback systems. This showed that the two workshops and two accelerator community groups benefit from synergies and contributed to networking between two different accelerator research fields. The workshop was jointly organized by the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI), SOLEIL and KIT, all are partners of I.FAST Task 7.2. As in the case of the Bunch-by-Bunch Feedback Systems workshop, the Injectors workshop resulted in relevant and sufficient scientific and technological conclusions with enhanced networking activities. The contents of the workshop were published on the Indico workshop website [8].

Workshop statistics:

21 presentations in 1.5 days, 41 participants from research areas

3 Other Networking Activities

3.1 JOINT EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN ON BUNCH-BY-BUNCH FEEDBACK SYSTEMS

Between the workshop on bunch-by-bunch feedback systems and the workshop on injectors, a joint experimental campaign [9] took place at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) in collaboration with partners from I.FAST Task 7.2 and the EU project EURO-LABS [10], where workshop participants conducted experiments at the Karlsruhe Research Accelerator (KARA), a 2.5 GeV electron storage ring, and its bunch-by-bunch feedback system, as well as in the 500 MeV booster. Beyond the preparation of the experimental campaign, the Task 7.2 team organized online meetings called Feedback Meetings to exchange information and knowledge about bunch-by-bunch feedback systems as a networking activity with feedback system specialists. The Feedback Meeting took place seven times until the joint experimental campaign, and the experimental topics and contents for the joint experimental campaign were discussed there and during the feedback system workshop to ensure the networking activity and search for relevant topics concerning the feedback system with the workshop participants. Three experimental topics out of eight suggestions were selected and conducted in a 1.5-day experimental period. The data and results have been shared with all interested participants, and the data analysis and subsequent discussions are ongoing.

3.2 POSTER PRESENTATION AT IPAC'24

In order to disseminate our networking activities worldwide, I.FAST Task 7.2 activities were presented on international conferences and workshops, e.g. gave a poster presentation at IPAC'24 entitled "Networking Activities of the I.FAST Project on High Brightness Accelerator for Light Sources", where the goals and networking activities of I.FAST Task 7.2 were presented. This presentation also aimed at networking not only in the field of low emittance rings, but also in other fields of accelerator physics and technology, such as hadron and linear accelerators. Several fruitful discussions took place during the poster session by inviting people from research and industry interested in networking activities. During the discussion, several people commented positively on the networking activities organized by I.FAST Task 7.2 and even asked about the next workshop plans. This clearly shows that our networking activities have a broad interest, impact, and contribute to the networking in the field of accelerator physics and technology, which are the goals of I.FAST Task 7.2. The poster presentation was a success, and its contents were published in the conference proceedings [11].

3.3 INVITED TALK AT IBIC'24

International Beam Instrumentation Conference (IBIC) 2024 [12], held in Beijing, suggested the participants of the bunch-by-bunch feedback workshop to give an invited review talk on bunch-by-bunch feedback systems by summarizing the feedback workshop held at KIT in March 2024. Upon receiving the suggestion, Dr. Takeshi Nakamura of KEK, one of the bunch-by-bunch system developers and workshop participants, presented his review talk entitled "Bunch-by-bunch feedback systems review," in which he summarized and presented the contents of the feedback workshop. The presentation showed many valuable discussions and conclusions we reached at the workshop and our

networking activities. Scientific board members of international conferences in particular,, in this case IBIC, became aware of our networking activities and nominated us as candidates for invited speakers. This means that our Task 7.2 activities have been widely recognized as worthy of attention. The presentation was a success, and the content of the presentation was published as a conference proceeding [13].

3.4 TASK REGULAR MEETING

To strengthen the networking activities in the field of ultra-low emittance rings, it is also essential that the members of Task 7.2 cultivate each other to accelerate the networking activities such as workshop organization. Based on the strategy, Task 7.2 organizes regular online meetings, which have been held since May 2021 and are organized monthly. In the monthly meetings, the Task partners, who are all specialists in accelerator physics and technology, discuss a wide range of topics in accelerator physics and technology and plans for workshop organization. This resulted in a scientifically friendly open exchange, through which the members generate workshops ideas during the scientific discussionsgs. The regular meetings held up to the end of January 2025 are listed below. To share the conclusions and discussions of the meetings, minutes and documents are prepared after each meeting and distributed to all Task partners.

No.	Meeting dates
1	05. May 2021
2	11. June 2021
3	15. July 2021
4	16. September 2021
5	13. October 2021
6	19. January 2022
7	16. February 2022
8	17. March 2022
9	13. April 2022
10	11. May 2022
11	24. June 2022
12	27. July 2022
13	31. August 2022
14	12. October 2022
15	18. November 2022
16	09. December 2022

No.	Meeting dates
17	19. January 2023
18	16. February 2023
19	24. March 2023
20	28. April 2023
21	31. May 2023
22	28. July 2023
23	08. September 2023
24	24. October 2023
25	24. November 2023
26	24. April 2024
27	29. May 2024
28	12. July 2024
29	22. November 2024
30	08. December 2024
31	19. December 2024

3.5 WORKSHOP PLAN: STABILITY OF STORAGE RING BASED LIGHT SOURCES

For future synchrotron light sources with ultra-low emittance beams, the stability of the light source is of paramount importance to exploit the properties of the high-quality beams. Beam stability issues have been addressed as one of the relevant topics in synchrotron light sources from hardware and beam dynamics aspects, including the time range from sub-microseconds to years. Based on this scientific motivation, Task 7.2 plans to organize a I.FAST Workshop on Stability of Storage Ring Based Light Sources in spring 2025. The goal of the workshop is to share the latest information and knowledge on beam dynamics to understand and improve beam stability and the hardware relevant to ensure stability of beam operation. During the workshop, a joint experimental campaign is planned at the Karlsruhe Research Accelerator (KARA) of the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, where participants can join in experiments related to light source stability. The organization of the workshop is ongoing, and according to the current workshop plan, the workshop will be held from 17 to 21 March at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Karlsruhe, Germany.

4 Conclusion

The objective of I.FAST Task 7.2 is to strengthen the networking in the field of ultra-low emittance rings. The partners of Task 7.2 actively organised workshops even during the challenging period due to the global pandemic, and joint experimental campaigns focusing on key technologies that are essential for the current and future ultra-low emittance rings. It can be said that the objectives of Task 7.2, namely networking, have been achieved to the extent that new networking has taken place with information exchange and synergy. Further networking activities will be intensified in the I.FAST project and also after the current project in order to establish technologies in the field of high-brightness synchrotron light sources.

5 References

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6 Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
I.FAST	Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology
CERN	Centre Européen des Recherches Nucléaires
EU	European Union
EURO-LABS	EUROpean Laboratories for Accelerator Based Sciences
IBIC	International Beam Instrumentation Conference
IPAC	International Particle Accelerator Conference
KARA	KARlsruhe Research Accelerator
KEK	Kō Enerugī Kasokuki Kenkyū Kikō, High Energy Accelerator Research Organization in Japan
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute for Technologie
LEAPS	League of European Accelerator-based Photon Sources is the network of all Synchrotron Radiation and Free Electron Laser user facilities in Europe
LEAPS-PerMaLIC	PerMaLIC is a LEAPS Internal Collaboration , a collaboration between the institutes of the LEAPS Consortium (https://leaps-initiative.eu), about development of Permanent Magnets for the future, ultralow emittance, light sources
NEG	Non evaporable getters (NEG) , based on the principle of metallic surface sorption of gas molecules, are mostly porous alloys or powder mixtures of Al, Zr, Ti, V and Fe.
PSI	Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland
SOLEIL	"Synchrotron SOLEIL", a non-profit civil French company created by the CNRS (National Centre for Scientific Research) and the CEA (Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission)